

The transfer of German pedagogical knowledge to Turkey through Turkish educators in the Early Republican Era: A historical social network study in the field of transnational education

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This study focuses on thirteen educators who were sent to Germany to study teaching and pedagogy in the late Ottoman and early Republican periods. The works of these individuals between 1923 and 1946 were analyzed to determine their educational ideas. In parallel, the thoughts of their German teachers were analyzed and historical social network analysis was applied between both groups. As a result of this analysis, the knowledge transferred by Turkish educators from their German teachers was obtained and how this knowledge was used or transformed was discussed.

The practice of sending students abroad emerged as an important parameter in Ottoman modernization (Erdogan, 2016). Since 1830, the Ottoman Empire sent students to Europe to receive education in different fields. In addition to the prominent specializations of the countries, Ottoman foreign policy was also a factor in this sending. As a result of the political and military rapprochement between Turkey and Germany in the late Ottoman period, the preference for Germany came to the fore (Yıldırım, 2005). This preference continued to be influential during World War I and after the establishment of the Republic. In particular, the preference for sending students to Germany to study teaching and pedagogy attracted attention (Aslan, 2014).

The aim of the research is to concretize the pedagogical knowledge transferred through the students sent to Germany by the state in the context of the developing educational relations between Turkey and Germany. In order to do this, it is to trace the process of knowledge transfer by monitoring the knowledge network between the students and their German professors. This will be done through the pedagogical phenomena and concepts identified in the publications and discourses of Turkish students after their return to their country.

The thirteen Turkish educators analyzed in this study received education in Germany in different periods. Therefore, they attended different teacher training institutions that developed within the history of German education. However, the common point of all of them is that they took part in the Turkish education bureaucracy between 1923 and 1946. They were commissioned by the state to prepare textbooks. They translated many works from German and put them into circulation in Turkish. On the other hand, they continued to communicate with their German teachers and with Germany itself. They closely followed the developments in the German education world. In general, they were all acquainted with the ideas of the new pedagogical movement in Europe. In addition, each of them adopted, followed and specialized in their own fields. For this reason, these thirteen educators were considered suitable for network analysis.

The written documents obtained in the research were first meticulously and systematically analyzed using the document analysis method (Wach, 2013). Thus, the necessary data were obtained from archival documents. Historical social network analysis method was used to analyze these data. In this analysis, the network between Turkish students and their German teachers, in other words, the structure formed by the relationships between individuals (Marsden, 2005) was obtained. In this historical network analysis, the network structure technique, which reveals all the structural features of the entire network, and the bond strength technique, which allows focusing on individual actors, were used (Öztaş & Acar, 2004).

In the part of the research conducted in Turkey, the necessary data were obtained from the state archives of the Presidency of the Republic of Turkey and the İsmail Hakkı Tonguç document archive. In the archival studies conducted in Germany, the archives of the cities where the students were sent, state archives, university archives and the Berlin Library-Archive of the History of Education were examined. In these examinations, the years the students were in Germany, the institutions they were sent to, their report cards, and the teachers they took lessons from were obtained. In addition, publications of both students and German teachers were included in the research as a source to determine their educational thoughts. In the determination of pedagogical thoughts, the limitation for German teachers was determined as the prominent works of the students in the years they took courses. The limitation for Turkish students was based on the year 1946 as the time interval determined in the research since their return to Turkey.

A network was formed between Turkish students and their German professors, which enabled the flow of information from German professors to Turkish students. Through this network, the pedagogical agendas of German professors, which were prominent in their educational ideas, were adopted by the Turks. Turkish students followed this knowledge after returning home. The networks were stronger in the types of information that were practical, easy and beneficial to apply. In this network, Turkish actors were connected to their German teachers in their ideas on collective education, rural education, arts education, vocational education, the combination of theory and practice for teacher training, and education for the state. This general framework will be customized for each actor and their teachers.

When the books of Turkish students were analyzed, it was seen that they knew the prominent pedagogical ideas of their time. In addition, they showed special interest in the world of German pedagogy. This can be seen in the bibliography they used for their works. The entire social network showed that they all advocated for German pedagogy in general. For each of them, it was seen that they followed their own understanding. On the other hand, although the books they translated were faithful to the text, they were technical works. In the works describing the theory of pedagogical thought, they did not stick to a single source. They supported the book they translated with other sources and produced a work that supported their own ideas. They stated this as preparing the book, not translating it. Based on this, it can be argued that they were trying to produce the knowledge needed by the Turkish education system or that they wanted to justify what the state expected from them.

While the research serves the aims of the discipline of comparative education (Kandel, 1955), it also has a transnational historical perspective that links the local with the global (Patel, 2009). The transnational ground of the research is provided by examining Turkish students as concrete carriers of knowledge. In this context, transnational history applied social network analysis.

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